

NEURAL NETWORK CONTROLLERS FOR THE X29 AIRCRAFT

Denis J.S.R. Bertrand
Canadian Armed Forces

Daniel J. Collins
Naval Postgraduate School
Monterey, California

ABSTRACT

Neural network structures have been developed to evaluate and control the X29 aircraft. The neural network evaluation of the unstable plant is coupled with an evaluation of an H_∞ controller for the aircraft to reproduce the dynamics of the aircraft. A controller based on the inverse of the plant is also investigated. This technique proved successful for the A4D aircraft but was not possible for the X29 aircraft.

I. Stable Systems and Stable Inverses

The X29 is a demonstrator fighter with a forward swept wing. The analogue backup mode of the plant, including short period dynamics and actuator dynamics, has 14 states and with the addition of a H_∞ controller the total system (plant and controller) has thirty states (1, Bertrand). There are two inputs the canard deflection and the joint deflection of flaperons and strakes. The two outputs are the angle of attack and the pitching rate q . Figure 1 shows a schematic of the system and the configuration used to train the neural network of the combined plant and H_∞ controller. The combined system is stable.

Closed-Loop Architecture

Figure 1 Closed-Loop Architecture

The neural network structure for this evaluation is shown in Figure 2.

MIMO Model Structure

Figure 2 MIMO Neural Network Model Structure

Note that the structure is linear with no hidden layers. There are 120 input nodes. Training was done by exciting the network with a random binary input with amplitudes of -1 and 1. The digitized system had a sampling time of .02 seconds. The pitching response of the neural network and the system are compared in Figure 3. Other responses were similar. Frequency domain comparisons were also excellent.

Figure 3 X29 Model and Network q Time Responses to Input 2 (Optimal case)

The inverse of the closed loop plant and controllers was also obtained since the system is stable with no non-minimum phase zeros. The effect of non-minimum phase zeros is discussed below.

II. Unstable Plant and Inverse

A more difficult task was to train separate neural networks for both the controller and the plant as shown in Figure 4. The training of the neural network for the H_∞ controller was straightforward since the controller is stable. The plant is however unstable. In order to train the network a small random step input of ± 0.01 was used and the inputs were reset to zero when the outputs reach ± 1 . After 25,000 epochs the neural network had learned to model the unstable X29 plant in the time domain, but the combination of both neural networks did not represent the system well.

Open-Loop Architecture

Figure 4 Open-Loop Architecture

The optimal controller has response times that exceed the capability of the aircraft actuators (2, Rogers). The response times are also about 4 times the sampling time. The linear neural network models did poorly in evaluating the controller plant combination. Two hidden layers were added to both models to yield an acceptable evaluation as shown in Figure 5 for q . Another controller designed for the X29 was also implemented through a neural network, but space precludes its discussion here.

III. Inverse Controllers

The inverse controller is an open loop controller. The inverse architecture is shown in Figure 6. After determination of the inverse the controller is implemented as shown in the bottom of Figure 6. The desired output is given to the inverse which generates the need inputs for the plant thus $y^1=y$.

Figure 5 X29 Optimal Controller Model and Network 1 q
Time Responses to Input 2 (2 Hidden layer)

Typical aerodynamic transfer function have non-minimum phase zero. The non-minimum phase zero became unstable poles in the inverse plant transfer function. It was possible to train a neural network for the unstable plant which had a discrete pole at 1.05. The inverse plant from the non-minimum phase zeros had, however, poles at -4.5, 2.2 and 9.5 (again in the z plane). We did not succeed in training the neural network for the inverse plant for the X29 due to the large instabilities of the inverse plant.

The large instability of the inverse poles causes the network to diverge rapidly. Frequent resetting of the network inputs to zero introduces a large noise component in the network weights. This is easily seen in frequency domain plots.

Inverse Plant Architecture

Figure 6 Inverse Plant Architecture

Since we had had success with the unstable X29 plant, a different system, the A4D aircraft, was tried. The A4D has (3, Scott and Collins) a stable 4th order plant with a non-minimum phase zero of 3.65. No actuator dynamics were considered. The plant was that of a discrete system with a sampling time of .1. The linear neural network architecture was used with the modification of increasing the outputs to 4 (u , α , q , and θ). Satisfactory emulation was obtained after 25,000 epochs. Figure 7 shows the rms error of the system to a random binary input. Note that the vertical scale is 10^{-4} .

In the case of the A4D the phugoid dynamics are also present in the model. To test the efficiency of the neural network in capturing the phugoid numerical transfer functions were determined using the spectrum function of Matlab. Training time had to be considerably increased and the phugoid dynamics were fairly captured.

Figure 7 RMS Prediction Error after 25K Epochs (case #4)

IV. Conclusions

For aerodynamic transfer function linear neural networks give excellent emulations. Neural networks can be trained for moderately unstable systems. The unstable system can be an original plant or an unstable inverse of the plant. For complex system involving multiple neural networks the normal nonlinear neural network with hidden layer appears better.

REFERENCES

- 1) Bertrand, Denis, J.S.R., "Application of Neural Networks to Adaptive Control Theory for Super-Augmented Aircraft", Aeronautical and Astronautical Engineers Degree, Naval Postgraduate School, Monterey, California, December 1991.
- 2) Rogers, W., "Application of Modern Control Theory Synthesis to a Super-Augmented Aircraft", Master of Science Thesis, Naval Postgraduate School, Monterey, California, June 1989.
- 3) Scott, R.W., Collins, D.J., "Neural Networks Adaptive Controllers", International Joint Conference on Neural Networks, San Diego, California, June 1990.